

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Impacts of Conditional Cash Transfer on Kalinga Women and Children: Evidence of a Randomized Survey

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Abstract

Background/Objectives: In the Philippines, the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) is a Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) that aims to help the poor by providing cash grants to beneficiaries. **Methods/Statistical analysis:** This study made use of mixed design, employing both quantitative approach for the use of a survey questionnaire and qualitative approach through a series of key-informant interviews held with beneficiaries', community leaders and members, and persons directly involved in the program's implementation. Focused group discussions were also conducted to assess the extent of community-driven development, women empowerment, and happiness well-being of the sample households. **Findings:** The study reveals that the respondents perceived that the CCT-4Ps program has a moderate impact on their lives and the identified weaknesses were perceived as moderately serious. For Kalinga's low-income families, the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program has a lot of compelling objectives, goals, and rewards. The 4Ps are an excellent illustration of how the government may improve its ability to allocate the country's resources to people who need them. It is evident that the mentioned program will benefit a large number of underprivileged families. The program meets fundamental requirements that would otherwise go unmet, and it mirrors the government's efforts to promote social mobility and equality. The 4Ps theory, according to the academics, states that well-fed and educated persons are essential for a prosperous country and society. The CCT-4Ps, on the other hand, is undeniably not the ideal solution. There are a number of flaws in the program that could cause it to fail in the long run. In the Kalinga, the 4Ps will undoubtedly require more adjustments and research in the future. **Novelty:** The study is a significant information to improve the implementation, specifically the selection, monitoring and improvement, of the 4Ps program in Kalinga Province.

Keywords: Conditional Cash Transfer; Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program; Kalinga Women; Randomized Survey; Philippines

1 Introduction

A Conditional Cash Transfer program is a government-run program in which money (cash grants) is distributed to eligible recipients. It is known as the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps)⁽¹⁾.

The CCT-4Ps was established to solve the country's poverty and inequality issues. The cash payments, which range from Php500 to Php1,400 per household per month depending on the number of qualifying children, are intended for chronically poor families with children aged 0 to 14 who live in disadvantaged neighborhoods. A social contract is at the heart of a CCT program, in which the state provides financial assistance to a family in exchange for the family's participation in certain activities, such as keeping at least 85 percent of its children in school, regularly visiting community health centers, participating in government-sponsored feeding programs, and attending more specialized training, to name a few⁽²⁾. The initiative is now seen as a "vehicle for improving government cooperation in supporting the needy and increasing the efficacy of social security services"⁽³⁾.

To fully understand its short-run effects, the motivations for the existence of such programs must be evaluated. Prevalent in today's society is households investing less in education and health care of children due to financial constraints. Hence, implementation of the CCT program in the Philippines and in less developed countries all over the world. Given this backdrop, the study focuses on the key question: what is the conditional cash transfer impact, particularly the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program Kalinga? This study was conducted to determine if the program is really fulfilling its objective that is to provide financial assistance in order to elevate the socioeconomic conditions of the poor members of the society. Likewise, many studies have been conducted on the impact of conditional cash transfer but there are no studies yet conducted on its specific effects to women and children in the Philippines.

In its initial impact evaluation, the initiative was found to be improving poor people's lives in general. As a result, it was resumed, although with certain changes. There was an increase in school attendance, as well as a decrease in the number of diseases among youngsters. Food expenditures in disadvantaged households grew as a result of the program, allowing family members to eat higher-quality food and consume more calories⁽⁴⁾.

Several studies have been undertaken in Mexico to assess the program's impact. In their study of the Mexican CCT known as the Education, Health, and Nutrition Program or Progresa, Skoufias and Parker attempted to evaluate the impact of the CCT on child work and school participation. Skoufias and Parker's analysis on the program notes outcomes that provide useful insight into elements such as time allotted for both leisure and work, in addition to the standard variables such as the incidence of child labor and participation in school levels. For children whose families received Progresa subsidies, it was discovered that school involvement increased while time spent working dropped⁽⁵⁾.

Another study by Rawling & Rubio⁽⁶⁾ backs up the assumption that CCT helps impoverished families in Mexico accumulate human capital. The increase in enrollment and attendance rates in the aforementioned countries demonstrates this. Girls' enrolment rates in Mexico's CCT program are anticipated to range from 7.2 to 9.3 percentage points, while boys' enrollment rates are estimated to range from 3.5 to 5.8 percentage points. The initiative also has a positive impact on the problem of child labor. In Mexico, the likelihood of working decreased by 10% to 1% among those aged 8 to 17. The effect is stronger for boys aged 12 to 14, with a 15 to 20% reduction in the likelihood of working, and the girls also show a considerable reduction in the likelihood of working.

The final effect of CCTs can be examined in terms of gender equality promotion. According to a research by Molyneux⁽⁷⁾, CCTs promote gender equality and women empowerment by granting financial transfers to women. Oportunidades promote women's equitable access to its benefits. Progresa's goal is to empower the beneficiaries' mothers and girls, as well as provide them the power to make decisions as family members. They feel that women's empowerment will improve the quality of life for families.

The 4Ps contributed a lot on the increase of enrollees of the school children. Mass participation of parents both in school and community activities are evident. They become more active participants in all activities held by the school like Brigada Eskwela and clean and green program of the barangay.

The grantees also gained knowledge on the processing of updates, grievance and complaints and the required supporting documents needed by the implementing agency by attending the monthly family development session by the municipal /city links. The grantees especially mother gain more knowledge on the different issues like disaster risk reduction, drug prevention, and child abuse during training where different speakers from different agencies are invited.

The impact of evaluation study was funded by the World Bank and the Australian Agency for International Development (AusAID). The study was led by the World Bank and the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), in coordination with AusAID and the Asian Development Bank (ADB).

Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program is a poverty reduction strategy that provides cash grant to poor households with pregnant women and children 0-14 without the conditions that they comply with specific conditions or health nutrition

education.

Objective:

1. To improve preventive health care among the pregnant women and young children.
2. To increase the enrolment and attendance rate of children in school.
3. To reduce the incidence of child labor.
4. To raise the average consumption rate in food expenditures of poor households.
5. To encourage parents to invest in their children’s human capital through investments in their health and nutrition, education, and participation in community activities.

Fig 1. The Conceptual Paradigm of the Study

2 Materials and Methods

This descriptive study examines the impact of the conditional cash transfer in Kalinga. It was conducted from January 2015 to June 2016 in the province of Kalinga.

The researchers started by understanding what CCTs are all about. They reviewed papers, documents, journals, and newspaper articles to understand how and why the Philippines embarked on this social program. To answer the research questions, the researchers conducted an informant interview, including Mrs.Digna Dalutag, Provincial DSWD Field Officer.

Requesting CCT-related papers and the identities of beneficiaries who would constitute part of the prospective responders from the provincial DSWD was the most difficult component of the fieldwork. The researchers were informed of the agency’s long-standing policy requiring approval from the Secretary of the Department before being given papers or allowed to interview personnel and beneficiaries. They decided to go forward with the interviews even though they didn’t have the formal documents and went through unauthorized routes.

The researchers conducted interviews with the beneficiaries during the quarterly releases of the cash benefits during the Landbank ATMs’ long queues.

Surprisingly, the beneficiaries were happy to answer the questions and even invited the researchers to their homes to see improvements in their lives because of the conditional cash transfer.

Participants

The province of Kalinga is composed of Tanudan, Tingalayan, Balbalan, Lubuagan, Pasil, Pinukpuk, Rizal, and the city of Tabuk. Northern Kalinga is composed of the municipalities of Balbalan, Pinukpuk, Tabuk, and Rizal.

The study’s survey component included 115 families who are beneficiaries of the 4Ps in the province of Kalinga. Of the 115 respondents, 26 were male, and 89 we female. The majority of the respondents were highly educated, with 68, while 47 were elementary-educated.

Data Resources and Analysis

This study used a questionnaire constructed by the researchers based on related literature and previous studies. Some indicators were adapted from a survey conducted by the DSWD in selected provinces, namely Lanao del Norte, Negros Oriental, and Occidental Mindoro, to enrich the questionnaire.

Its qualitative information was collected through a series of key-informant interviews held with beneficiaries’ other community leaders and members, and persons directly involved in the program’s implementation. Focused group discussions were also conducted to assess the extent of community-driven development, women empowerment (role in household decision-making, reduction of domestic violence and allocation of time used for household chores and childcare), and happiness well-being of the sample households.

Frequency counts and percentages were used to determine the patterns of impacts. The survey questions on impacts include both positive and negative impacts of the program and the program’s weaknesses.

Impacts and weaknesses reported by more than 40% of the respondents were only presented on the result tables. In scoring, the average score was calculated for each subject impact, and then this score was re-encoded as low impact (indicated by the average score of 1.00 to 1.66), moderate (1.67 to 2.33), high (2.34 to 3.00). The overall mean score for the sub-categories of impacts was then calculated.

The information gathered was meticulously collated, sorted, analyzed, and interpreted using the statistical techniques below: frequency and percentage were utilized to determine the impacts and weaknesses. The CCT-4Ps’ levels of impact, on the other hand, were described using the Weighted Mean.

3 Results and Discussion

Impacts of the CCT-4Ps on Kalinga Women and Children

Table 1. Impacts of the Conditional Cash Transfer: 4Ps (N=115)

Impacts	% of Responses	Mean	Description
A. Positive			
Fewer missed meals	46	1.60	Low impact
Lower rates of underweight children	61	1.75	Moderate impact
Fewer reported sicknesses	59	1.97	Moderate impact
Higher school enrolment and fewer absences	94	2.37	High impact
Better access to medicines and health care	85	2.20	Moderate impact
Improved situation of women	92	2.43	High impact
Empowerment of women	90	2.15	Moderate impact
Lessened incidence of child labor and other forms of child abuse	93	2.25	Moderate impact
Percentage within category/Sub-mean	77.5	2.08	Moderate impact
B. Negative			
Created dependence	51	1.68	Moderate impact
Reduced incentive to work	52	1.53	Low impact
Community conflict	93	2.38	High impact
Misguided spending	95	2.41	High impact
Percentage within category/Sub-mean	72.75	2.00	Moderate impact
Percentage within all categories/TAWM	75.13	2.05	Moderate impact

The study reveals that the respondents received that the CCT_4Ps program has a moderated impact on their lives. Positive impacts, although described as moderated, obtained a slightly higher mean of 2.08. The negative impacts registered a mean of 2.00, which also falls under the moderate description.

Among the positive impacts, improved situation of women (2.43) and higher school enrolment & fewer absences (2.37) are described as high impact.

The CCT-4Ps can be regarded to have improved children’s attendance at school. With the program’s requirement of 85% monthly attendance for all students aged 6 to 14, parents are now the ones encouraging their children to go to school. Parents who were once passive tutors and prodders of their children are now active tutors and prodders of their children not to be absent. The program also serves as a tool for teaching parents. While the children are at school, the women attend parenting seminars, family planning workshops, and nutritional classes, among other things, quenching their desire for knowledge and hunger for information. They did not understand until the Pantawid Familyang Pilipino Program came into the picture. A teacher in an elementary school said that the CCT-4Ps helped improve children’s school attendance, especially during the planting and harvesting seasons. Children are called to work either to lessen expenses on paid labor or to have more opportunities to increase income for the family. It was also noted that parents’ mass participation in school and community activities is also evident. They become more active participants in all school activities like Brigada Skwela and the clean and green program of the barangay.

The situation of women also improved. This is because of the CCT_4Ps target households with women and children. The women beneficiaries claimed that with the CCT-4Ps, they could make decisions regarding the family’s finances. They also

claimed that the additional money the CCT-4Ps enable them to indulge in some of their whims, such as buying lipstick and other women things. More importantly, they b=now have confidence in facing the realities of life since they are assured of the government’s support, especially on health and education matters. The grantees, especially mothers, gain more knowledge on the different issues like disaster risk reduction, drug prevention, and child abuse by attending the monthly family development session by the municipal/city links where different speakers from different agencies are invited.

The identifies negative impacts were rated as moderate, as shown by the mean of 2.00. misguided spending (2.41) and Community Conflict were rated as high impact. The FGD participants mentioned that grantees of the CCT-4Ps exhibited symptoms of misguided spending in their respective areas. One woman-grantee spent the family’s allowances on set a set of (kaldero) cauldrons. It must be noted that a set of cauldrons of varying sizes is a source of prestige for Kalinga households.

Elementary school teachers also complain that children of 4P grantees still come to class without necessary supplies such as paper, pencil, and even worse, not footwear despite the conditionalities about education.

On this note, key informants revealed that parents ensure their continued membership in the CCT-4Ps by complying with the conditionalities, including sending their children to school. It doesn’t matter whether they have things such as paper, pencils or snacks. Being in school is what is important.

FGD participants also generally observed that during the scheduled release of the 4Ps allowance, the sale of alcohol in sari-sari stores increases, and the incidence of drunkenness is reported at the various barangay councils in Kalinga. Family disputes and cases of abuse towards women and children are also recorded.

Community disputes emanating from the implementation of the 4Ps are also noted as high impact. This is because middle-income community members resent their exclusion from the program since they claim that they also suffer from financial problems. They also resent that their taxes are being given to families that are just lazing around waiting for the release of their allowances. Some low-income families also qualify for the 4 Ps but were excluded because they could not comply with the documentary requirements and claim favoritism in the targeting/selection process. According to some members of the community...

“Pinipili da lng ti nagipaka-ammuan da dita, digidiay lang ammo da nga nagnibutos kinyada ti angibagaanda.” (information was disseminated only to their political allies and their relatives)

Weaknesses in the implementation of the CCT in Kalinga

Table 2. Weaknesses of the Conditional Cash Transfer: 4Ps (N=115)

Weaknesses	% of responses	Mean	Description
Changes in political leadership and program administration	92	2.30	Moderately serious
Difficulties in developing the program management information system (MIS)	51	2.34	Very serious
Insufficient access to information	65	2.36	Very serious
Targeting errors	94	2.49	Very serious
Noncompliance with 4Ps conditions	74	2.02	Moderately serious
Payment errors	82	1.69	Moderately serious
Inefficient in grievance resolution processes	89	1.63	Less serious
Ineffective monitoring system	93	2.46	Very serious
Lak of clarity/transparency on Exit or graduation	65	2.36	Very serious
Ineffective control and accountability mechanism	91	2.45	Very serious
Percent with all categories/TAWN	79.6	2.21	Moderately serious

The identified weaknesses were perceived as moderately serious, as evidenced by the Total Average weighted mean of 2.21. Six (6) of the weaknesses were rated as very serious, while three (3) were rated moderately serious. Only one is targeted as less serious.

One important feature of the program is targeting of beneficiaries which, as advocates have repeatedly declared, is objective, transparent, and uniform (Valerde and Fernandez, 2011), thereby minimizing, if not avoiding, leakage and under coverage problems, as well as abuse by the politicians and local bosses. The targeting approach, according to Fernandez and Olfindo (2011), is a multi-step process in which the poorest provinces are chosen based on poverty data collected by the National Statistics Office’s Family Income and Expenditure Survey (FIES) (NSO). The poorest municipalities/towns within the chosen province are chosen based on the poverty data produced by the National Statistical Coordination Board’s Small Area Estimates (SAE) (NSCB). The cities, on the other hand, are chosen based on poverty data collected by the Presidential Commission for the

Urban Poor (PCUP). Poor households are identified within the designated barangays using a household targeting system that mostly relies on proxy means tests (PMT). This test categorizes families based on proxy characteristics such as access to water and sanitation, household head's education, livelihood, asset ownership, and home style⁽⁸⁾. Finally, based on the qualifying criteria, possible beneficiaries' households are identified. Before any names are enrolled as program beneficiaries, the list of these families is publicized at the barangay hall for community validation.

On the surface, targeting appears to be objective and unbiased. Nonetheless, the DSWD's primary source disclosed that for the third expansion, some barangays had to be included as target areas since some politicians complained that they were being left out of the program because their residents were impoverished and deserving of help. On the other hand, some FGD members questioned why many of their poor neighbors, if not poorer than their families, had been left out of the program. As one participant observed....

“Toan po nu paman na bulon mi un paat pagay kapos nu dikani pun adidapon naiyala si sana en bumaloan.” (I couldn't help but ask why a neighbor who is even poorer than our family has not been included in this program)

Supposedly, the Pantawid Pamilya is monitored by the Municipal Link with the BLGU, RHU, and Dep-Ed help. Compliance with the conditions stated by the Pantawid Pamilya is the basis of the amount that will be given to the grantees. Noncompliance with one or more of the conditions cannot be avoided, although there are penalties for failure to comply with the condition. If this is done repeatedly, it will eventually result in dismissal from the program. Every two months, education (children aged 3 to 14), health (children aged 2 to 5), and attendance at the Family Development Seminar (FDS) are all monitored. The compliance of the health conditions is monitored by the doctor, nurse, and midwife, as well as the Municipal Link (ML) and Parent Leader (PL). The principal or the teacher, on the other, sees the compliance with the education conditions. The ML visits school and health facilities within the municipality every two months to collect the Compliance Verification (CV) form indicating the record of obedience to the program conditions. These records will be on the total amount cash grant the family will be receiving.

However, our key informant mentioned that these processes demand time, effort, and resources from personnel who have other functions in their respective agencies. Monitoring is often delegated to a person who is not trained on the procedure involved. More often, local government officials are tasked to monitor the 4Ps families in their area. This practice compromises the monitoring system's reliability since local government officials tend to become subjective in their reports.

Another very serious weakness of the CCT-4Ps is insufficient access to information. Many households could not handle the many conditions they had to complete since they were not efficiently educated about the program. Studies were done in other countries also determined the delays or even failures can also be caused by the difficulties in developing the program Management Information System (MIS).

In contrast with previous related studies, the implementation of the conditional cash transfer in Kalinga province in particular, is the regular monitoring and evaluation of the designated agencies to determine if the program is really serving its purpose. In addition, the families who have been beneficiaries of the program for many years could have graduated now in order to accommodate new beneficiaries.

4 Conclusion

Based on the general findings of the study, the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program has moderate impact among the Kalinga women and children with 2.05 mean. It is undeniable that many poor households benefitted from the said program. The program covers the basic needs that otherwise would go unmet—Likewise, the government's effort in making social mobility and equality. The researchers strongly feel the 4Ps principle that well-fed and educated citizens are imperative for a productive country and society.

However, it is undeniable that the CCT-4Ps is not the perfect solution as the weaknesses were found moderately serious with 2.21 mean. There are many insufficiencies that the program might face in the long run of its implementation. And in the Kalinga, the 4Ps will certainly need further revisions and studies in the future.

Nonetheless, the experts feel that every government program must be based on a peaceful agreement between the government and population. People's needs must be satisfied, and their rights must be protected, according to the government. Citizens, on the other hand, must utilize their full potential in order to be productive and contribute to the country. Implementing the 4Ps, according to experts, is a good example of the government and the general people sharing responsibility.

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